

Deliverable D7.2

Analysis of distributed data for cancer research

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents a series of use cases in the oncological domain which can be used to test the GDI proposed platform and therefore query, retrieve and analyse distributed data.

The use cases were designed together with clinicians in order to achieve maximum plausibility and adherence to a specific set of final users' needs. Datasets are entirely synthetic, so that their usage is not impaired by legal frameworks protecting the privacy of European citizens.

The use cases are composed of a short clinical description, alongside standardized synthetic genetic and clinical data, and can be freely downloaded from the Zenodo repository. This deliverable describes three single-patient use cases and one multi-patient use case, to mimic a multi-node query, thus addressing several different types of cancer and clinical questions and needs by the community.

The datasets can be thought of as the results of specific queries over the GDI platform, assembling virtual cohorts that can be analysed (mainly inspected) by the user.

The main challenge was the standardization of the clinical data and the alignment with the work packages tasked to create the platform.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	No

<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Methods

In order to create use cases in the oncological domain, which are relevant for researchers, and especially clinicians in the field, and useful to test the developing technological infrastructure, we conducted a series of surveys with the members of the 1+Million Genomes Working Group 9 (cancer applications). The aim of these surveys was to collect the needs of the final users of the platform, transform them into use cases, and create the corresponding synthetic datasets to test the use cases.

The use cases created were composed by a brief description of their goals, a synthetic genetic dataset (in the variant calling format, thus containing the genetic alterations found in a cancer sample), and a corresponding clinical dataset. The clinical data were collected according to the 1+MG Minimal Dataset for Cancer scheme (1, which we developed and published last year) and stored in YAML format, where essential information about the patient was stored. Datasets were inspired by real patient cases, yet are completely synthetic to prevent any legal issue about the privacy of the patients.

Synthetic genetic datasets were created from synthetic genomes, where variants of interest were introduced with the BamSurgeon (2) tool, with the exception of UC1 (Malignant Melanoma), where we used genetic data from an existing cell line (COLO-829). Variants were then called with the Mutect2 (3) software tool.

Synthetic clinical datasets were manually curated according to the specificities of the synthetic genetic datasets, mimicking the relevant information for the use case, such as patient's history and treatments. Datasets were collected following the conventions and rules of the 1+Million Genomes Minimal Dataset for Cancer model (1), and exported according to the GA4GH Phenopackets (4) standard.

All the material referring to the different use cases has been uploaded on the Zenodo repository and can be found at the following URLs:

- UC1: Malignant Melanoma <https://zenodo.org/records/15754092>
- UC2: Chronic Myeloid Leukemia (CML) <https://zenodo.org/records/15754623>
- UC3: Non Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) <https://zenodo.org/records/15754200>
- UC4: Pancreatic cancers <https://zenodo.org/records/15754326>

The use cases were prepared in close collaboration with WP8 in Pillar III (Applications and Innovation solutions, lead Salvador Capella-Gutierrez), WP6 in Pillar II (Data Management, lead Rob Hooft), and WP2 in Pillar I (Long term sustainability, lead Regina Becker), and connected by a parallel initiative driven by the GDI Pillar II partners, illustrated in this video <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tkklC2k14lc>.

4. Description of work accomplished

Here is a brief summary of the work accomplished, which is detailed below:

- Creation of “Single-patient cancer use cases”
- Creation of “Multi-patient cancer use cases”
- Relationship with GDI user journeys

4.1 The need

The grand objective of the European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project is the realization of a platform where genetic and potentially associated clinical data can be stored, queried, accessed and re-used across Europe. This endeavour leverages on the insights previously produced within the 1+Million Genomes initiative and the pioneering Beyond One Million Genomes project, which set the stage for the current effort.

Within the previous projects, and even more within GDI, it is imperative that the working groups/packages (WPs) tasked with creating the infrastructure, composed mostly with IT experts, keep a close contact with the final users of the infrastructure, satisfying the needs of these communities. Use-cases working groups within 1+MG and work packages from Pillar III within GDI, must feed these needs to the infrastructure makers. The situation is further complicated by the existence of several distinct types of users, with different needs and requests: as we concentrate here on the oncology use case, we adopt the point of view of clinical oncologists and, partly, of basic oncology researchers.

These two communities typically approach genetic data differently: while a basic researcher is generally interested in testing original hypotheses on available data, which often require a complete reanalysis of the dataset with custom pipelines, in the healthcare setting the priority is to identify patients similar to case at hand, and inspect the presence of additional genomic variations, specific clinical features and administered treatments to gauge the outcome following a specific clinical path. This, in turn, makes the clinical dataset accompanying the genetic data even more essential for the needs of an oncologist interested in perusing the genetic datasets stored within the GDI infrastructure. The use cases presented in this document can be used to identify patients with specific genomic and clinical characteristics by querying a GDI-like federated infrastructure; the datasets can also be downloaded to be analysed with specific pipelines, although their synthetic nature can hinder the outcome of some analyses (i.e. in UC2 and UC3 the computational discovery of large-scale genomic rearrangements may lead to coarse errors due to inaccuracies in the construction of the synthetic genome).

As we discussed above, it is crucial to provide clinical data together with genetic data in the oncology setting. As clinical data can be collected with a plethora of devices (from pen and paper, to free-text pdf documents, to databases), to achieve interoperability it is imperative to choose a data model with specific fields where variables take values within specific dictionaries. For the use cases

we generated, we supplied some clinical data according to the 1+MG Minimal Dataset for Cancer (1) model, exported according to the Phenopackets standard (4).

Finally, it has to be noted that human data in Europe is regulated under the GDPR framework, which limits the possibility of sharing sensitive datasets where individuals can be reidentified, as it is the case from complete genomic sequences. To test a computational platform, it is, therefore, extremely useful to prepare some with synthetic data, which are not subjected to GDPR and that can be readily used and transferred.

Each use case will be then composed by three items:

- A brief description of the case
- A genetic dataset
- An associated clinical dataset

4.2 Single-patient cancer use cases

The simplest cases collected in our survey represent a typical situation where a clinician looks into the GDI federated infrastructure for patients with specific characteristics, similar to an in-house patient, in order to compare/be inspired about the clinical management of the case. The infrastructure responds to the query from one of the nodes, where the query is matched. When the GDI platform will be up and running, it is realistic to expect that the platform will respond with more than one node, so here we can envision the situation of a very rare cancer type. In fact, this first batch of use cases are useful also to the IT community building the platform, as they can be used to test the federated infrastructure, mimicking the data discovery and retrieval, on the backdrop of a realistic oncological case in a clinical setting. Intentionally, we did not go into details about the technical subtleties allowing a data governance compliant with GDPR and national rules, leaving it to specialists in the field to address this sensitive point: the main purpose of this document is to provide a series of datasets that could be used by the community to test federated data-sharing infrastructures with realistic queries and situations. Some of these use cases were partly described in Deliverable D7.5, and they are all inspired by real cases discussed in molecular tumour boards or within oncological wards. Finally, these cases can also represent the situation when a basic researcher assembles a small cohort to download and reanalyse the datasets, although with the limitations described above.

4.2.1 Melanoma

The first use case describes a patient diagnosed with malignant melanoma. Initial molecular analysis showed at the time of diagnosis the BRAF V600E somatic mutation (that is pervasive in this cancer type). The patient was treated with the standard of care BRAF inhibitor Vemurafenib. After 4 months of therapy, the patient stopped responding: a new specimen of the tumour was sequenced, and a deletion on the PTEN gene was found. A clinician wants then to find a similar case to investigate new therapies and to find the molecular alterations explaining the insurgence of the resistance. The query

is then for a patient with 1) malignant melanoma 2) with a relapse 3) resistant to Vemurafenib 4) with a deletion in the PTEN gene.

The genetic datasets are derived from the COLO-829 and COLO-829-BL cell lines (thanks to Ed Cuppen from the Hartwig Medical Foundation, the Netherlands) and consists in two BAM files containing the aligned reads (tumour/normal samples), a variant calling format file containing the genome variants, in particular the BRAF V600E Single Nucleotide Variation, and a BED file containing the intervals of the copy number variation, in particular a 12kb deletion within the PTEN gene, and a clinical data file, according to the Phenopackets standard, both in JSON and YAML format. Please note that the files containing genetic data are linked in the Zenodo record, as they have already been uploaded elsewhere.

4.2.2 CML

The second use case, developed in collaboration with Richard Rosenquist from the Karolinska Institute in Stockholm, describes a patient presenting some generic symptoms, with an enlarged spleen, and abnormal blood cell counts. Subsequent tests confirmed that the patient is affected by a blood cancer, Chronic Myeloid Leukemia, expressing the e14a2 BCR-ABL1 transcript (b3a2 subtype). The patient received Imatinib as a first line treatment, which gave a good clinical response and was maintained for 36 months, when the symptoms returned. The genetic dataset is synthetic, created with the BAM Surgeon tool (thanks to David Torrents from the Barcelona Supercomputing Center) and consists of a VCF file containing the genetic alterations of the patient at the time of the relapse, while the clinical dataset is in YAML format, collected according to the Phenopackets standard.

4.2.3 Non Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC)

The third use case describes a patient diagnosed with a NSCLC, stage IVb adenocarcinoma. The tumour is positive for a ROS1 fusion but negative for BRAF mutations (assessed with PCR techniques). It was treated with Crizotinib but after 12 months the patient stopped responding and the tumour progressed. A complete sequencing of the tumour genome through a biopsy showed a BRAF V600E mutation and the disappearance of the ROS1 fusion. Again, the oncologist wants to find similar patients in the database to get inspiration about new therapies and to understand why the first line therapy stopped working. The query consists then in 1) NSCLC 2) ROS1 positive at diagnosis 3) treated with Crizotinib 4) with a BRAF V600E mutation after the resistance to the therapy.

The genetic dataset is synthetic and created with the BAM Surgeon tool (thanks to David Torrents from the Barcelona Supercomputing Center) and consists of several CRAM files containing the aligned reads (tumor/normal), a VCF file containing the genetic alterations of the patient at the time of the relapse, while the clinical dataset is in YAML and JSON formats, collected according to the Phenopackets standard.

4.3 Multi-patient cancer use case

All the use cases described so far are based on a simple, yet not completely realistic, hypothesis: the query entered by the user is answered only by one node of the network, and therefore it gives back a dataset referring to a single patient. While this is perfectly useful for testing a computational platform, a more realistic scenario would entail a request to the entire network with more than one dataset present on separated nodes.

Indeed, as cancer types are more and more characterized with genetic and clinical details, the constellation of clinical and genetic details would lead to smaller and smaller populations. In other words, it is as if specific cancer types could be considered rare diseases for which a limited set of patients is available.

4.3.1 Pancreatic cancers

In this use case, we consider three distinct datasets, all related to pancreatic cancers and all generated from real-world clinical cases:

- 1) A male patient presents with abdominal pain and weight loss. After radiological detection of a mass and a histological inspection of a bioptic sample, the patient is diagnosed with a pancreatic acinar cell carcinoma with a neuroendocrine subclone. The patient received first line chemotherapy with Folfirinox, which only slowed down the tumour growth. A complete sequencing of the tumour showed a low tumour mutational burden, microsatellite instability and a complex BRAF alteration (V600_K601delinsE), and three variants of uncertain significance in the genes POM121L12, MGA, STK11.
- 2) A female patient presents with yellowing of the sclera, abdominal pain and weight loss. Imaging showed an abdominal mass, which was diagnosed as a pancreatic adenocarcinoma. The patient received first line therapy with PAXG, which stopped working after 6 months. The patient was then eligible for second line chemotherapy with liposomal irinotecan. Genetic testing showed a CUX1-BRAF fusion and 16 somatic gene variants.
- 3) A male patient presents with persistent lumbar pain, weight loss and altered levels of pancreatic and liver enzymes. Imaging revealed a pancreatic mass. The patient received gemcitabine and nab-paclitaxel, but progressive disease was the best result after 3 months. Genetic testing showed a large number of single nucleotide gene alterations.

For all the patients, genetic data is present under the form of VCF files containing the genetic alterations, and clinical data is collected according to the Phenopackets standard in YAML format.

This small cohort of patients can be the outcome of a query on pancreatic cancer containing alterations in BRAF gene, to show the diversity of diseases and treatment outcomes that can be driven from specific changes in the gene. For example, a user can query the platform on several fields, like the disease type (pancreatic cancer), tumor type, genomic alteration or comorbidities. Depending on the complexity of the query, the system can respond with one, two or three matches.

4.4 Relationship with user journeys

Some of these use cases have been used in Deliverable 7.5 (5), where they were projected on the so-called “user journeys”. While this document describes realistic cancer datasets available for testing any infrastructure, Deliverable 7.5 uses some of these datasets to describe the journey of a user - not only interested in cancer - within the GDI platform in development.

5. Results

- Several synthetic datasets, paired to cancer use cases have been created.

The main result of this deliverable is the generation of several synthetic datasets that can be freely downloaded and used to mimic the work of

- oncologists looking for patients with genetic and clinical characteristics similar to those of their own patients, or
- basic oncology researchers assembling a cohort of cases with the same features.

From the clinical point of view, this can lead in turn to several crucial insights on the best treatment for a patient, about new potential therapies or about the role of some (combination of) genetic alterations in dictating the outcome of a disease or the response to therapy. On the other hand, an oncology researcher can dig deep into such datasets to find genetic characteristics leading to a better understanding of basic oncology mechanisms. The GDI platform must be able to accommodate these specific users' needs.

With three single patient datasets (malignant melanoma, chronic myeloid leukemia and non small cell lung cancer, respectively) and one multi-patient dataset (pancreatic cancer) we provide here a varied collection. Each dataset is composed by genetic data (variant calling format files containing gene alterations, and in some cases also BAM files containing aligned reads and BED files containing insertions and deletions), clinical data (clinical items, collected according to the 1+MG Minimal Cancer Dataset model in Phenopacket format, saved in a JSON or YAML file), and by a user story describing the case.

These datasets have been presented multiple times within GDI events, but also at conferences (EHSG) and at events related to different initiatives (ELIXIR, EOSC4Cancer, the Italian Health Big Data initiative, the Alleanza Contro il Cancro Network, etc.).

6. Discussion

- Use cases were built with the point of view of a clinical oncologist in mind, and they can be used to check whether the GDI platform can satisfy the needs of these users. At the same time, they also represent a subset of the needs of a basic oncology researcher.
- Clinical data must be standardized to allow queries in the platform

The main challenges faced to build these use cases are twofold:

- 1) First, use cases come with a purpose and with an audience. It is impossible to create all-purpose use cases, which serve several potential objectives at the same time. Our use cases have as a main purpose the testing of a federated infrastructure from the point of view of a final clinical user in the oncological field, remaining as realistic as possible. We had extensive interactions with clinicians to write use cases inspired by real world situations, and we listened to their real world problems to create situations that closely mimicked clinician doubts and questions. However, they can be used also by computer scientists developing a platform to check whether its specifics match what is required from the users. The case of basic researchers using the platform is slightly more complex, as the range of questions that can be asked and analyses that can be performed is far larger. The use cases described in this document may be suited to address some of these needs, but in this case it would be preferable to build new use cases around specific research questions.
- 2) Another large, incumbent problem is the standardization of clinical data. While genetic data are output by (typically the same type of) instruments and are therefore highly standardized, clinical data are collected by human beings, through a plethora of different means. This generates datasets that are collected with different data models, in different formats, in different languages, which are useless for structured queries. We used the 1+MG Minimal Cancer Dataset (1) data model to standardize the relevant clinical information, using well-described fields with values varying within controlled vocabularies. We recommend collecting clinical data in the most standardized possible fashion, so that they could be imported, possibly after an automatic translation carried out by some middleware, straight into the platform database.

7. Conclusions & Impact

- The described use cases are a valuable asset to test the GDI platform
- The platform must account for all the final users' needs

We consider the datasets described in this Deliverable as valuable assets for the working packages tasked with building the platform, and we hope for a similar series of use cases for the other foreseen applications (infectious diseases, rare diseases, etc.) that could guide the infrastructure makers.

The biggest risk of a project as large and complex as GDI is probably the disconnection between its different moving parts, especially if time runs short and deadlines are close. The worst possible scenario would be where the IT experts lose sight of the applications of the infrastructure and build a platform which is formally and internally coherent and neat, but that does not allow the final users to perform the queries and the tasks they need. This would lead to a complete failure, as the final platform would not be used by many people and would quickly die or languish for a few years before getting abandoned.

It is therefore imperative that working packages in Pillar II (tasked to create the infrastructure) keep a tight communication channel with those in Pillar III (tasked with designing applications), but also with those in Pillar I (tasked to create the legal and governance framework) in order to comply with European laws about privacy and data protection.

8. Next steps

We envision the following next steps:

- 1) Using the Secure Processing Environments that will be provided by the nodes, perform data visualization and reanalysis on the virtual cohorts assembled by the queries.
- 2) Produce new use cases, according to the needs of the project, possibly representing different types of users (basic researchers, etc.).
- 3) Keep a close communication with the other working packages, especially those in Pillar II
- 4) Investigate the legal framework for using real human datasets, which is the final aim of the GDI project.

9. References

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